

Flexible Communication Platform for Crisis Management

Authors : Jiří Barta, Tomáš Ludík, Jiří Urbánek

Abstract : The topics of disaster and emergency management are highly debated among experts. Fast communication will help to deal with emergencies. Problem is with the network connection and data exchange. The paper suggests a solution, which allows possibilities and perspectives of new flexible communication platform to the protection of communication systems for crisis management. This platform is used for everyday communication and communication in crisis situations too.

Keywords : crisis management, information systems, interoperability, crisis communication, security environment, communication platform

Conference Title : ICDEM 2014 : International Conference on Disaster and Emergency Management

Conference Location : Istanbul, Turkey

Conference Dates : December 05-06, 2014